

Spectro-analytical studies on (*E*)-*N'*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)benzohydrazide and its interaction with Cu^{II}

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Abstract : The ligand (*E*)-*N'*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)benzohydrazide formed a green coloured complex with Cu^{II} metal. The composition of complex was determined spectrophotometrically, by employing Job's and mole ratio methods in ethanol medium. Both the experiments confirmed 1 : 1 stoichiometry of metal complex. Potentiometric studies were carried out in 70% v/v ethanol-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M ionic strength. The pH curves of free ligand and 1 : 1 metal-ligand systems indicated number of dissociable protons in ligand. The study revealed the dissociation of one proton in free ligand and two dissociable protons in presence of Cu^{II} ion due to complexation. The solid Cu^{II}-complex was synthesized and characterized by mass and IR data. The mass spectrum displayed a molecular ion peak corresponding to 1 : 1 metal-ligand composition. The comparison of IR data in ligand and metal complex, inferred chelating properties of ligand.

Keywords : (*E*)-*N'*-(2-Hydroxybenzylidene)benzohydrazide (H₂ sal-bhz), Cu^{II} metal, Job's method, mole ratio method, mass spectrum, IR spectrum, dissociation constant.

Introduction

The derivatives of *N'*-benzylidene benzohydrazide and their metal complexes have been a subject of intensive research due to their novel structural features¹. Their complexes have a variety of applications in biological, clinical and analytical fields². Recently there has been a considerable interest in the chemistry of hydrazine and hydrazone compounds because of their potential pharmacological applications³.

The remarkable biological activity of aroyl hydrazides R-CO-NH-NH₂, their corresponding aroyl hydrazones R-CO-NH-N=CHR, and also their mode of chelation with transition metal ions has aroused interest in the past due to possible biomimetic applications. The coordination compounds of aroyl hydrazones have been reported as enzyme inhibitors and are useful due to their pharmacological applications⁴.

The purpose of this study is to comprehend the chelation properties of (*E*)-*N'*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)benzohydrazide by employing various spectro analytical techniques viz. mass, IR, spectrophotometry and pH-metry.

The infrared studies on iron complexes of title compound were reported earlier⁵. These studies indicated dissociation of only phenolic proton of compound upon complexation. The present study throw an insight, on bonding modes as well as dissociable protons in the title compound on reaction with Cu^{II}.

Results and discussion

An attempt was made to establish the metal to ligand ratio in green coloured complex formed from H₂ sal-bhz and copper ion, by adopting Job's and mole ratio methods of spectrophotometric technique.

Job's continuous variation method :

The solutions of the Cu^{II} and H₂ sal-bhz with same molar concentrations (0.00125 M) are mixed in varying volume ratios, keeping the total volume of the mixture constant. The pH of solutions is maintained constant by adding 3 ml of CH₃COONa + CH₃COOH (0.00125 M) buffer. The absorbance of each solution is measured at wavelength 450 nm (λ_{max}). The absorbance is plotted against the mole fraction of the ligand. The resulting curve

showed a maximum absorbance value at 0.5 mole fraction of ligand (Fig. 1). The calculated mole fraction values and absorbance are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of absorbance versus mole fraction of ligand at 303 K in ethanol medium.

free ligand (0.001 M) and metal-ligand (metal 0.001 M and ligand 0.001 M) at 303 K temperature by maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1 M in 70% v/v ethanol-water medium (Fig. 3).

The free ligand curve indicated release of one proton with pK_a value of 9.70. The proton released can be attributed from phenolic hydroxyl group. However the dissociation of second proton is also evident from metal ligand curve ($m = 2$). This is attributable to dissociation of enol proton via keto-enol tautomerism in $-CO-NH-N=C-$ group apart from proton dissociation from phenolic group during complex formation. The results confirm that the ligand can bind with metal ion by releasing two protons. The finite participation of these sites from which protons dissociated enables the imine nitrogen also

Table 1. Data showing the mole fraction of ligand and absorbance values of Cu^{II} and H_2 sal-bhz system in ethanol medium at 303 K

Sl. no.	Cu^{II} solution (ml)	H_2 sal-bhz solution (ml)	Buffer (ml)	Total volume (ml)	Absorbance (A)	Mole fraction
1.	2	18	5	25	0.048	0.9
2.	4	16	5	25	0.098	0.8
3.	6	14	5	25	0.163	0.7
4.	8	12	5	25	0.231	0.6
5.	10	10	5	25	0.282	0.5
6.	12	8	5	25	0.221	0.4
7.	14	6	5	25	0.155	0.3
8.	16	4	5	25	0.1	0.2
9.	18	2	5	25	0.048	0.1

*Acetate buffer (0.00125 M) is used to maintain pH of the solutions constant.

Mole ratio method :

A series of solutions are prepared, in which the molar concentration of metal ion is kept constant while that of the H_2 sal-bhz was varied. The pH of solutions was maintained constant by adding acetate buffer. A plot of the absorbance versus number of moles of the H_2 sal-bhz per mole of Cu^{II} ion showed two straight lines of different slopes. The mole ratio value at intersection of two lines corresponds to composition of the metal complex (Fig. 2). The data of absorbance versus mole ratio is given in Table 2.

Equilibrium studies :

Potentiometric titrations have been carried out with

Fig. 2. Plot of absorbance versus mole ratio of ligand at 303 K in ethanol medium.

Table 2. Data showing the mole ratio of ligand and absorbance values of Cu^{II} and H₂ sal-bhz system in ethanol medium at 303 K

Sl. no.	Cu ^{II} solution (ml)	H ₂ sal-bhz solution (ml)	Buffer (ml)	Absorbance (ml)	Concentration of ligand	Concentration of metal	Mole ratio [L]/[M]
1.	2	0.5	5	0.04	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0001	0.25
2.	2	1	5	0.078	5 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0001	0.5
3.	2	1.5	5	0.119	7.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0001	0.75
4.	2	2	5	0.158	1 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	1
5.	2	2.5	5	0.165	1.25 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	1.25
6.	2	3	5	0.173	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	1.5
7.	2	3.5	5	0.179	1.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	1.75
8.	2	4	5	0.185	2 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	2
9.	2	4.5	5	0.192	2.25 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	2.25
10.	2	5	5	0.198	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0001	2.5

*Acetate buffer (0.00125 M) is used to maintain pH of the solutions constant.

Fig. 3. pH titration curves of (i) H₂ sal-bhz (0.001 M), (ii) Cu^{II} (0.001 M) + H₂ sal-bhz (0.001 M) at 303 K and $\mu = 0.1$ M KNO₃ in 70% v/v ethanol-water medium; m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

to coordinate with metal ion to result in the formation of 5 and 6 membered ring chelate (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

Thus equilibrium studies reveal that the ligand coordinates to the metal ion in a binegatively tridentate manner. The co-ordination takes place through enolate oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and phenolate oxygen.

Characterisation of the complex :

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum of H₂ sal-bhz displayed peaks of ν_{NH} and ν_{OH} at 3268 cm⁻¹ and 3366 cm⁻¹ respectively (Table 3). A comparative study of the IR spectra of H₂ sal-bhz and its Cu^{II} complex reveals the absence of OH (phenolic) and NH (amide) peaks in complex spectrum indicating the release of two protons upon complex formation. The peak at 1509 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum of Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex attributable to -C=N indicates the shift of double bond from carbonyl carbon to amide nitrogen

proton. Thus $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{NH}-$ proton dissociation occurs via enol form. A shift in $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of imine group (azomethine) from 1606 cm⁻¹ in ligand to 1599 cm⁻¹ in Cu^{II} complex infers^{6,7} the participation of the imine nitrogen in bonding with Cu^{II}. Thus imine nitrogen atom, phenolic and enolic oxygen atoms are the potential binding sites in H₂ sal-bhz. The appearance of broad band around 3431 cm⁻¹ in the complex has been assigned to associated water molecule. Appearance of a medium intensity band at 758 cm⁻¹ in the metal complex is assignable to rocking mode due to coordinated water molecule⁸. Some new bands of weaker intensity in complex at 560 cm⁻¹ and 460 cm⁻¹ give inference about $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ bonding⁸.

Table 3. IR and mass spectral data of H₂ sal-bhz and Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex

Compd	IR data (cm ⁻¹)						Mass data (<i>m/z</i>)
	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{CH(aromatic)}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{OH(H}_2\text{O)}}$	
H ₂ sal bhz	3366	3268	3065	1606	1621	-	241 242
Cu ^{II} H ₂ sal-bhz	-	-	3062	1599	-	3431	302 304
				1509			

Mass spectrum

The mass spectrum of H₂ sal-bhz shows dominant molecular ion peak at *m/z* 241, which is in accordance with the expected protonated molecular ion (M+H)⁺. The protonated ions are expected because the sample was analyzed under positive ionization conditions. Hence the measured molecular mass (240 amu) deduced is in good agreement with the theoretical value. The mass spectrum of H₂ sal-bhz also contains adduct peaks at *m/z* 263 and *m/z* 264, corresponding to 23 mass units higher than the expected molecular mass. These can be attributable to sodium adduct ions, (M+Na)⁺ and (M+1+Na)⁺ respectively.

The mass spectrum of Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex exhibited a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 302 which is in accordance with 1:1 composition of Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex. This spectrum also shows ⁶⁵Cu isotopic peak at *m/z* 304. Thus mass spectral data of Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex confirms the existence of 1:1 metal ligand composition. The results of IR and mass spectral data of the ligand and metal complex are given in Table 3.

Conclusions

The various methods employed in the study indicate the formation of 1:1 Cu^{II}-sal-bhz complex. The results from Job's and mole ratio methods signify the formation of 1:1 metal complex in solution. The mass spectral data of solid Cu^{II} complex is quite informative to deduce the structure of metal complex. Equilibrium studies revealed that metal complex formation is accompanied by the release of two protons. Comparison of IR data of ligand and metal complex gave evidence for complex formation.

Experimental

The compound H₂ sal-bhz was synthesized in two steps⁹. The first step involves synthesis of benzoyl hydrazide by refluxing equimolar mixtures of hydrazine hydrate (5 ml, 0.1 mole) and ethyl benzoate (15 ml, 0.1

mole) in 25 ml of absolute ethanol on a water bath for 4-6 h. Second step involves refluxing of the benzoyl hydrazide (1.36 g, 0.01 mole) with salicylaldehyde (1.22 ml, 0.01 mole) in 20 ml of ethanol along with a drop of conc. H₂SO₄. This mixture was refluxed for half an hour, upon cooling and slow evaporation the compound H₂ sal-bhz was formed. Purity of the compound was monitored by TLC using silica gel G (m.p. 163-164 °C).

Cu^{II}-sal-bhz was prepared by mixing cupric chloride to the 50 ml methanolic solution of title compound in 1:1 molar ratio. The resulting mixture was then refluxed on water bath for half an hour. The precipitated complex was recrystallized with ethanol, finally washed with petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out on a SL-171 Minispec recording spectrophotometer, one centimeter cells were used in the instrument. IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 435 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on Micro Mass VG70-70H spectrometer operating at 70 eV using direct inlet system, were recorded.

Measurements of pH were made with a pH meter equipped with a glass and reference electrode couple. The pH measurements were made using digital Digisun 707 pH meter consisting of a combined glass electrode and calomel electrode (reading with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit). The instrument was calibrated with standard buffers (pH 4.00, 7.00 and 9.20) with appropriate temperature corrections. High precision constant temperature bath was used to maintain temperature constant. The mercury regulator was of auto booster type and maintained with an accuracy of ± 0.010 °C by circulating water through the outer jacket of the reaction cell.

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